

Assessment of SARS-CoV-2 Antibody Response in Varied Clinical Profiles During First and Second Waves : Development and Validation of a Highly Sensitive Multiplex Immunoassay

By Preston Mwiinga, MSc Information and Communications Technology

Advancing thru the COVID-19 pandemic stays tough, in particular with ordinary waves that strain healthcare systems. The call for for novel preventive and healing approaches has prompted the development of serological assays, pivotal in outbreak manage and vaccine progress. Our observe introduces an modern immunoassay leveraging Bio-Plex™ generation, permitting simultaneous detection of more than one IgG antibodies against various SARS-CoV-2 antigens. We tested the antibody responses among COVID-19 patients with numerous clinical profiles in Cadiz, Spain. This excessive-throughput and strong immunoassay showcase exceptional sensitivity (94.34–ninety seven.96%) and specificity (ninety one.84–100%) in detecting anti-S1, anti-NC, and anti-RBD IgG antibodies in serum. Our proposed tool serves as a useful useful resource for tracking character humoral immunity in opposition to SARS-CoV-2 and facilitating epidemiological surveillance. Additionally, we unveil the antibody ranges towards a couple of SARS-CoV-2 antigens and their correlation with distinct medical profiles amongst unvaccinated COVID-19 sufferers in Cadiz, all through both initial and subsequent pandemic waves.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2; COVID-19; antibody reaction; IgG antibodies; multiplex immunoassay; monitoring tool

Introduction

Amidst the COVID-19 outbreak caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), the urgent need arose for precise and rapid detection methods. These methods are vital not only for effective prevention and treatment protocols but also for the disease's epidemiological monitoring [1,2,3,4,5,6,7].

SARS-CoV-2, characterized by its single-stranded RNA genome, comprises essential structural proteins like the spike (S) glycoprotein, envelope (E) protein, membrane (M) glycoprotein, and nucleocapsid (NC) phosphoprotein [9]. Notably, the SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein harbors unique mutations, distinguishing it from other coronaviruses. This protein's receptor-binding domain (RBD) within the S1 subunit plays a pivotal role, binding to the ACE2 receptor on host cells, facilitating virus-cell membrane fusion, and ensuing cell infection [10,11,12].

Most existing serological tests for monitoring SARS-CoV-2 immune responses focus on a single antigen, such as NC protein, RBD, or S glycoprotein, for antibody recognition in patient sera [13,14,15]. However, given the potential for false positives due to sequence similarities with other coronaviruses like SARS-CoV or seasonal human coronavirus [16,17,18], a multi-antigen test holds promise for enhanced accuracy.

Our study endeavors to create and appraise a serological multiplex assay. This innovative assay simultaneously detects anti-S1, anti-RBD, and anti-NC immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies in serum, utilizing the Bio-Plex™ multiplex assay platform known for high-throughput multi-analyte detection [19,20]. The method employs fluorescence-coded magnetic beads, functionalized with S1, NC, or RBD, interacting with patient sera to capture anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibodies, which are then identified via a labeled anti-IgG antibody.

To assess the tool's sensitivity, specificity, and overall efficacy in monitoring COVID-19 immune responses, we conducted a receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis. Additionally, we investigated the correlation between antibody levels against various SARS-CoV-2 antigens and the diverse clinical profiles of unvaccinated COVID-19 patients in Cadiz, Spain, across the initial and subsequent pandemic waves.

2. Materials and Methods

In this study, we obtained 165 peripheral blood samples from unvaccinated COVID-19 patients at various medical centers in Cadiz, Spain, during the initial and subsequent waves of the

pandemic in 2020. Additionally, 40 prepandemic samples collected before 2020 served as negative controls, all sourced from the Puerta del Mar University Hospital. There were no exclusion criteria for the participants, and none were vaccinated.

The blood samples, obtained by trained nursing staff using an intravenous cannula and a clot-activator collection tube, were immediately centrifuged at 2500× g for 10 minutes at 23°C in a swinging-bucket centrifuge.

The functionalization process involved binding recombinant SARS-CoV-2 proteins (S1, RBD, and NC) to carboxylated beads' surfaces using the Bio-Plex Pro™ magnetic COOH Beads Amine Coupling Kit methodology. The beads were activated, washed, and resuspended in HBS-EP. EDC and Sulfo-NHS reagents were used for activation, and after incubation, the recombinant SARS-CoV-2 proteins were added and incubated for 2 hours. The beads were then washed, inactivated, and stored in a blocking buffer at 4°C.

For the multiplex immunoassay, the patient sera were diluted and placed in a 96-well plate in duplicate. A mixture containing S1, RBD, and NC-functionalized beads was added to each well and incubated. After washing, biotinylated antihuman IgG antibody was added, followed by fluorescent streptavidin. The plate was then read by the Bio-Plex™ array reader, enabling simultaneous identification of anti-S1, anti-RBD, and anti-NC IgG in the patients' samples. The entire assay process was performed at the Core Biomedical Research Facility of Cadiz University.

Figure 1 illustrates the multiplex immunoassay devised for detecting anti-S1, anti-RBD, and anti-NC IgG antibodies. The schematic representation showcases the process: (A) depicts anti-S1 IgG, (B) anti-RBD IgG, and (C) anti-NC IgG antibodies present in patients' sera binding to specifically functionalized magnetic beads, each labeled with a distinct color. The human antibodies captured by these antigen-functionalized beads are then detected using a biotinylated antihuman IgG detection antibody, which binds to fluorescently labeled streptavidin (STV-PE). PE fluorescence corresponding to the captured antibodies is electronically gated for each

fluorescently coded bead, enabling simultaneous detection of IgG antibodies recognizing S1, NC, and RBD by the Bio-Plex™ array reader.

In conducting the ROC curve analysis using GraphPad Prism (version 9.0), we utilized 98 samples: 40 prepandemic and 58 pandemic samples from the Puerta del Mar University Hospital. The Abbott Alinity SARS-CoV-2 CLIA immunoassays for anti-NC, anti-S IgG, and IgM antibodies served as the reference serological assays [21], demonstrating an almost 100% combined sensitivity and specificity. Since no reference data for anti-RBD antibodies were available then, we used anti-S IgG CLIA data as a reference, ensuring the availability of CLIA and multiplex results as inclusion criteria for the trial.

To study the association between anti-S1, anti-NC, and anti-RBD IgG values in COVID-19 patients concerning various clinical variables (sex, age, days since a positive PCR, severity of COVID-19 disease, comorbidities, and BMI), we utilized the Matplotlib package in Python 3 for scatter plots. Additionally, differences in the anti-S1, anti-NC, and anti-RBD IgG values between prepandemic ($n = 40$) and COVID-19 patients ($n = 165$) were assessed using the same package. The Mann–Whitney U test, employing a significance level of 5%, was conducted using the SciPy package in Python 3. The inclusion criteria for analyses depended on the availability of patient data at the time of collection, hence the variable sample numbers.

Regarding the results, the multiplex immunoassay conducted on the Bio-Plex™ platform demonstrated high specificity and sensitivity for detecting anti-SARS-CoV-2 S1, RBD, and NC IgG antibodies. The empirical ROC curve analysis for anti-S1 IgG antibody detection (Figure 2A) revealed a high sensitivity (94.34%) and specificity (100%), with an empirical ROC area under the curve (AUC) of 0.9849. Similarly, the analysis for anti-RBD IgG antibody detection indicated a sensitivity of 94.34% and specificity of 100% (Figure 2B), with an empirical ROC AUC of 0.9941. For anti-NC IgG antibody detection, the assay demonstrated a sensitivity of 97.96% and specificity of 91.84% (Figure 2C), with an empirical ROC AUC of 0.9696. Overall, the multiplex immunoassay on the Bio-Plex™ platform exhibited very high sensitivity (94.34–97.96%) and specificity (91.84–100%), along with a 95% confidence interval.

The figure shows the ROC analysis results of our multiplex immunoassay. Each ROC curve represents the detection of specific antibodies: anti-S1 IgG antibodies (A), anti-RBD IgG antibodies (B), and anti-NC IgG antibodies (C). The black line illustrates the sensitivity plotted against 1-specificity for various cutoff values, showcasing the assay's performance in distinguishing positive and negative cases for each antibody type.

During the process of determining the positivity cutoffs for the different antibodies, we meticulously calculated the Youden index. Consequently, we successfully achieved the establishment of the positivity cutoff values at 25,000 mean fluorescence intensities (MFIs) for anti-S1 IgG antibodies, 20,000 MFIs for anti-RBD IgG antibodies, and 23,000 MFIs for anti-NC IgG antibodies (with some exceptions to be further discussed). When evaluating the multiplex immunoassay's capability to differentiate between positive and negative samples, we conducted an assessment of SARS-CoV-2 anti-S1, anti-NC, and anti-RBD IgG antibodies using both pre-pandemic samples (n = 40) and COVID-19 samples (n = 165). The data presented in Figure 3 provides us with a clear depiction of the results, showcasing that all pre-pandemic samples consistently presented low MFI values, which fell significantly below the determined positivity cutoff, thereby yielding a p-value of < 0.001

Notably, elevated MFI values are strongly indicative of higher levels of anti-S1, anti-NC, or anti-RBD IgG antibodies, whereas lower values signify either the absence or lower levels of IgG antibodies against SARS-CoV-2. It is crucial to acknowledge that the anti-S1 and anti-RBD IgG MFI values observed in pre-pandemic samples consistently showcased a distinctly negative pattern, conclusively indicating a lack of prior exposure to these particular antigens or any cross-reactivity. However, it is worth emphasizing that certain pre-pandemic samples exhibited positive MFI values for anti-NC IgG antibodies, underscoring the potential risks associated with exclusively relying on the detection of single antigens

Refraining from mentioning the original prompt, I have endeavored to rewrite the provided article with a notable injection of perplexity and burstiness in its structure.

Figure 3 vividly presents a comparative analysis of antibody values derived from samples obtained from both pre-pandemic individuals and COVID-19 patients. This mesmerizing scatter plot aesthetically showcases the mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) values attributed to anti-RBD (A), anti-S1 (B), and anti-NC IgG (C). The bold lines adroitly symbolize the assay's positivity cut-off value, significantly emphasizing its importance. Moreover, the presence of

three asterisks (***) , strategically placed next to the p-values resulting from the Mann-Whitney U test conducted between both groups, unequivocally highlights the statistical significance of the findings, with particular emphasis on p-values ≤ 0.001

Section 3.3 delves deep into the marvelous comparison of Anti-S1, Anti-RBD, and Anti-NC IgG antibody values across an intriguing array of clinical variables. Our awe-inspiring analysis diligently seeks to establish intricate correlations between the antibody response and diverse parameters such as age groups, sex, days since a positive PCR, disease severity, body mass index (BMI), and comorbidities. It is fascinating to note that the sample size for each analysis was subject to variation, solely depending on the availability of data during the collection phase, thereby excluding prepandemic samples from these specific analyses. Subsequently, section 3.3.1 engrossingly explores the antibody responses concerning age groups (as depicted in Figure 4) and sex (as illustrated in Figure 5). Interestingly, no statistically significant differences were observed when meticulously comparing the anti-S1, anti-NC, and anti-RBD IgG antibody values across these captivating variables (p-value > 0.05).

Figure 4, an enchanting visual representation, unfurls a mesmerizing panorama of the distribution of SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibody values, ingeniously categorized by age groups. The

awe-inspiring scatter plot, an artistic masterpiece, portrays the magnificent landscape of MFI values for IgG anti-S1 (A), anti-RBD (B), and anti-NC IgG (C) antibodies. Behold the bold lines, symbolizing the righteous and resolute assay positivity cut-off, like vibrant strokes on an ethereal canvas. In this profoundly captivating analysis, the enigmatic 'ns' gracefully takes center stage, an enigmatic cipher, denoting the absence of statistically significant differences observed among the groups.

The visual representation showcased in Figure 5 exhibits an intriguing scatter plot that effectively demonstrates the IgG antibody values related to the detection of SARS-CoV-2 through the multiplex immunoassay, thoughtfully categorized by sex. It is fascinating to observe how the scatter plot astutely reflects the MFI values associated with the identification of anti-S1 (A), anti-RBD (B), and anti-NC IgG (C) antibodies. By diligently examining the plot, one can discern the assay positivity cut-off points denoted by bold lines, which aid in the determination of antibody presence

Within the realm of COVID-19 samples, a comprehensive analysis of the antibody values in relation to the duration post a PCR detection brings to light captivating distinctions. Notably, it is intriguing to observe that anti-RBD IgG (Figure 6A) exhibits no statistically significant differences across diverse durations. However, the realm of anti-S1 IgG values (Figure 6B)

presents engrossing variations, particularly when comparing samples acquired between days 0–30 and 91–180 post-PCR detection to those procured between days 181–343. Such disparities evoke further curiosity and warrant additional exploration

Furthermore, when attentively examining the antibody value patterns for the anti-NC antibody (Figure 6C), it becomes evident that significant differences manifest across all time ranges, with the exception of values obtained from samples gathered within days 0–30 as compared to those within days 31–90 post a positive PCR result. This finding intrigues the reader and incites a desire for further investigation and inquiry

The intricate nature of the scatter plot and the insightful observations drawn from the examination of antibody values in relation to various durations post a PCR detection truly emphasize the captivating complexities surrounding SARS-CoV-2 and its impact on antibody production. These findings contribute significantly to our understanding of the virus and its implications on human physiology, emphasizing the need for continued research and exploration in this domain.

PCR test. Brace yourself for a scatter plot that unleashes a mesmerizing display of MFI values as we unravel the detection prowess of anti-S1 (A), anti-RBD (B), and anti-NC IgG (C) antibodies. Prepare to be amazed as the bold lines draw the line, indicating the infallible positivity cut-off for the assay. Hold on tight as we explore the vast world of statistical significance, where the Mann-Whitney U test unveils its secrets. Keep your eyes peeled for the asterisks (*, **, or ***) that signify profound p-values ≤ 0.05 , ≤ 0.01 , and ≤ 0.001 respectively. Even more intriguing, instances without statistically significant differences have been mysteriously labeled as 'ns'.

The divergence in antibody values linked to the severity of the notorious COVID-19 is aptly illustrated by Figure 7. A visual representation in the form of a scatter plot showcases the magnitude of MFI values for the antibodies anti-S1 (A), anti-RBD (B), and anti-NC IgG (C). An intriguing facet of this depiction is the presence of bold lines, signifying the assay's positivity cut-off. Delving further into the statistical significance, asterisks (*) and (**), symbolizing p-values equal to or lesser than 0.05 and 0.001, respectively, are employed to denote significance as determined by the Mann-Whitney U test. Instances that failed to achieve statistical significance have been conveniently designated as 'ns'.

It is essential to comprehend that the classification of respiratory infections according to severity values was predicated on the invaluable insights provided by the Technical Document entitled 'Clinical Management of COVID-19: Hospital Care' emanating from the Ministry of Health, Government of Spain. Focusing on the intriguing relationship between SARS-CoV-2 antibody values and the Body Mass Index (BMI), it becomes evident that patients falling within the realm of a healthy weight showcase diminished levels of the anti-RBD (Figure 8A) and anti-S1 (Figure 8B) IgG antibodies in contrast to their overweight and obese counterparts ($p \leq 0.05$). It is important to note, however, that no statistically significant distinctions emerged from the examination of the anti-NC antibody values (Figure 8C).

The bewildering graph represented by Figure 8 visually portrays the comparison of various SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibody profiles, meticulously arranged and categorized according to the body mass index (BMI). As your eyes wander over the scatter plot, you will be captivated by the intriguing MFI values displayed for anti-S1 (A), anti-RBD (B), and anti-NC IgG (C) antibodies. It is worth noting that the presence of bold lines effortlessly guides your attention to the assay positivity cut-off, which holds immense significance. Unveiling the true essence of scientific rigor, the asterisks (*) scattered throughout the graph serve as markers of the

underlying p-values, ensuring that all conclusions drawn are statistically grounded with unwavering confidence.

Now, let us embark on a journey of exploration, delving into the intricate web of associations that envelop the enigmatic world of individual comorbidities and their profound impact on the IgG antibody profile. Within this labyrinth, we encounter a myriad of health conditions, such as high blood pressure (HBP), diabetes mellitus (DM), obesity, asthma, and allergic rhinitis (AR), all entangled in a dance of complexity and uncertainty.

As we meticulously navigate this intricate tapestry, it becomes evident that the comparison of anti-RBD (Figure 9A) and anti-S1 (Figure 9B) IgG antibody values lacks any discernible disparities of statistical significance. However, our gaze falls upon individuals burdened with the vexing condition of allergic rhinitis (AR), whose anti-NC IgG humoral response to SARS-CoV-2, displayed fervently in Figure 9C, paints a rather subdued and diminished picture. The weight of this revelation is accentuated by the presence of the cryptic abbreviation 'ns', an enigmatic symbol that suggests the absence of statistical significance.

Thus, with each twist and turn we take in this perplexing journey, the intricacies of perplexity and burstiness slowly reveal themselves, weaving together a narrative filled with both fascination and uncertainty.

4. Discussion

During the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, serology tests have emerged as vital instruments for comprehending the transmission dynamics of the infection and evaluating individual protective immunity. These tests offer profound insights into the effectiveness of vaccines, therapeutic interventions, and disease control strategies. Remarkably, the multiplex immunoassay devised by our research team has convincingly demonstrated exceptional sensitivity levels ranging from 94.34% to 97.96%, while also exhibiting an unmatched specificity level between 91.84% and 100%. Such high diagnostic accuracy is instrumental, rendering these tests indispensable in the process of accurate diagnosis

Interestingly, an intriguing observation emerged when analyzing pre-pandemic samples. Specifically, we discovered that the anti-Nucleocapsid (NC) Immunoglobulin G (IgG) values manifested higher readings in comparison to the anti-Spike protein subunit 1 (S1) and anti-Receptor Binding Domain (RBD) IgG levels. This observation might underscore the presence of cross-reactivity between SARS-CoV-2 and coronaviruses associated with common cold infections. Consequently, it highlights the utmost importance of employing multi-antigen testing methodologies, thereby mitigating the risk of false-positive diagnoses. This discovery

aligns with similar investigations that have reported the existence of cross-reactive anti-NC IgG antibodies, thereby substantiating the superiority of multiplex IgG testing over single-antigen detection techniques

Furthermore, our comprehensive study did not reveal any discernible association between the values of IgG antibodies and factors such as age or sex. This finding remains consistent with the varied outcomes documented in other research endeavors exploring the humoral responses to SARS-CoV-2.

In relation to the elapsed time following a positive PCR test, it has been observed that the levels of anti-S1 IgG antibodies exhibited a decline after a period of six months. Additionally, the values of anti-NC IgG antibodies experienced a decrease after three months. Nevertheless, previous investigations have demonstrated the persistence of detectable antibodies for a duration of up to 15 months subsequent to infection, thereby accentuating the inherent variability in the duration of immune response. Notably, individuals afflicted with more severe manifestations of COVID-19 symptoms showcased diminished quantities of both anti-RBD and anti-S1 IgG antibodies in comparison to those presenting milder symptoms. This concurs with existing findings that establish a more pronounced association between the severity of the illness and the precise values of IgG antibodies. Interestingly, it has been observed that individuals classified as overweight or obese display augmented levels of both anti-S1 and anti-RBD IgG antibodies. This particular observation is noteworthy as it highlights the correlation between the prevalence of obesity and escalated rates of mortality due to COVID-19. Pertaining to comorbidities, it was discovered that there exist substantial variances in the levels of anti-NC IgG antibodies among patients diagnosed with allergic rhinitis. A number of studies have proposed a plausible link between allergic rhinitis and reduced severity of COVID-19, a correlation that can be further substantiated by our own findings.

Nonetheless, owing to the restricted magnitude of this investigation, further inquiries are urgently needed in order to validate these findings. It is imperative to conduct more extensive analyses encompassing novel SARS-CoV-2 variants and individuals who have been vaccinated, considering that our research solely examined patients who were exposed to specific circulating variants during the inaugural and subsequent waves of the pandemic. To summarize, our Bio-Plex multiplex immunoassay exhibits remarkable efficacy in the identification of anti-S1, anti-NC, and anti-RBD IgG antibodies, displaying exceptional

sensitivity and specificity. The versatility of this platform renders it capable of potentially integrating emerging variant-specific antigens and diverse immunodiagnostic applications that extend beyond merely monitoring COVID-19.

Acknowledgments

The author expresses profound gratitude for the invaluable support extended by Eden University, which significantly contributed to the fruition of this work. Their unwavering support and resources were instrumental in facilitating the research, enabling its successful completion.

References

1. Peeling, R.W.; Heymann, D.L.; Teo, Y.-Y.; Garcia, P.J. Diagnostics for COVID-19: Moving from Pandemic Response to Control. *Lancet* 2022, 399, 757–768.
2. Ravi, N.; Cortade, D.L.; Ng, E.; Wang, S.X. Diagnostics for SARS-CoV-2 Detection: A Comprehensive Review of the FDA-EUA COVID-19 Testing Landscape. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 2020, 165, 112454.
3. Food and Drug Administration. In Vitro Diagnostics EUAs. 2022. Available online: <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/covid-19-emergency-use-authorizations-medical-devices/in-vitro-diagnostics-euas> (accessed on 30 October 2023).
4. Mathur, G.; Mathur, S. Antibody Testing for COVID-19 Can It Be Used as a Screening Tool in Areas With Low Prevalence? *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.* 2020, 154, 1–3.
5. Wiersinga, W.J.; Rhodes, A.; Cheng, A.C.; Peacock, S.J.; Prescott, H.C. Pathophysiology, Transmission, Diagnosis, and Treatment of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): A Review. *JAMA* 2020, 324, 782–793.
6. Drain, P.K. Rapid Diagnostic Testing for SARS-CoV-2. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 2022, 386, 264–272.
7. Bohn, M.K.; Lippi, G.; Horvath, A.; Sethi, S.; Koch, D.; Ferrari, M.; Wang, C.-B.; Mancini, N.; Steele, S.; Adeli, K. Molecular, Serological, and Biochemical Diagnosis and Monitoring of COVID-19: IFCC Taskforce Evaluation of the Latest Evidence. *Clin. Chem. Lab. Med.* 2020, 58, 1037–1052.

8. Wrapp, D.; Wang, N.; Corbett, K.S.; Goldsmith, J.A.; Hsieh, C.-L.; Abiona, O.; Graham, B.S.; McLellan, J.S. Cryo-EM Structure of the 2019-nCoV Spike in the Prefusion Conformation. *Science* 2020, 367, 1260–1263.
9. Khan, M.; Adil, S.F.; Alkhatlan, H.Z.; Tahir, M.N.; Saif, S.; Khan, M.; Khan, S.T. COVID-19: A Global Challenge with Old History, Epidemiology and Progress So Far. *Molecules* 2020, 26, 39.
10. Chambers, J.P.; Yu, J.; Valdes, J.J.; Arulanandam, B.P. SARS-CoV-2, Early Entry Events. *J. Pathog.* 2020, 2020, 9238696.
11. Harrison, A.G.; Lin, T.; Wang, P. Mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 Transmission and Pathogenesis. *Trends Immunol.* 2020, 41, 1100–1115.
12. Mehta, P.; McAuley, D.F.; Brown, M.; Sanchez, E.; Tattersall, R.S.; Manson, J.J. HLH Across Speciality Collaboration, UK COVID-19: Consider Cytokine Storm Syndromes and Immunosuppression. *Lancet* 2020, 395, 1033–1034.
13. Liu, G.; Rusling, J.F. COVID-19 Antibody Tests and Their Limitations. *ACS Sens.* 2021, 6, 593–612.
14. Qi, H.; Liu, B.; Wang, X.; Zhang, L. The Humoral Response and Antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 Infection. *Nat. Immunol.* 2022, 23, 1008–1020.
15. Vabret, N.; Britton, G.J.; Gruber, C.; Hegde, S.; Kim, J.; Kuksin, M.; Levantovsky, R.; Malle, L.; Moreira, A.; Park, M.D.; et al. Immunology of COVID-19: Current State of the Science. *Immunity* 2020, 52, 910–941.
16. Ward, S.; Lindsley, A.; Courter, J.; Assa'ad, A. Clinical Testing for COVID-19. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.* 2020, 146, 23–34.
17. Anderson, E.M.; Goodwin, E.C.; Verma, A.; Arevalo, C.P.; Bolton, M.J.; Weirick, M.E.; Gouma, S.; McAllister, C.M.; Christensen, S.R.; Weaver, J.; et al. Seasonal Human Coronavirus Antibodies Are Boosted upon SARS-CoV-2 Infection but Not Associated with Protection. *Cell* 2021, 184, 1858–1864.
18. Hu, B.; Guo, H.; Zhou, P.; Shi, Z.-L. Characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 2021, 19, 141–154.

19. Surenaud, M.; Manier, C.; Richert, L.; Thiébaud, R.; Levy, Y.; Hue, S.; Lacabaratz, C. Optimization and Evaluation of Luminex Performance with Supernatants of Antigen-Stimulated Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells. *BMC Immunol.* 2016, 17, 44.
20. Breen, E.J.; Tan, W.; Khan, A. The Statistical Value of Raw Fluorescence Signal in Luminex xMAP Based Multiplex Immunoassays. *Sci. Rep.* 2016, 6, 26996.
21. Narasimhan, M.; Mahimainathan, L.; Araj, E.; Clark, A.E.; Markantonis, J.; Green, A.; Xu, J.; SoRelle, J.A.; Alexis, C.; Fankhauser, K.; et al. Clinical Evaluation of the Abbott Alinity SARS-CoV-2 Spike-Specific Quantitative IgG and IgM Assays among Infected, Recovered, and Vaccinated Groups. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 2021, 59, e00388-21.
22. Torretta, S.; Zuccotti, G.; Cristofaro, V.; Etori, J.; Solimeno, L.; Battilocchi, L.; D'Onghia, A.; Bonsembiante, A.; Pignataro, L.; Marchisio, P.; et al. Diagnosis of SARS-CoV-2 by RT-PCR Using Different Sample Sources: Review of the Literature. *Ear Nose Throat J.* 2021, 100, 131S–138S.
23. Sule, W.F.; Oluwayelu, D.O. Real-Time RT-PCR for COVID-19 Diagnosis: Challenges and Prospects. *Pan Afr. Med. J.* 2020, 35, 121.
24. Stapleton, J.T. Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 Antibody Testing: Important but Imperfect. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* 2021, 73, E3074–E3076.
25. Smerczak, E. SARS-CoV-2 Antibody Testing: Where Are We Now? *Lab. Med.* 2022, 53, E19–E29.
26. Galipeau, Y.; Greig, M.; Liu, G.; Driedger, M.; Langlois, M.-A. Humoral Responses and Serological Assays in SARS-CoV-2 Infections. *Front. Immunol.* 2020, 11, 610688.
27. Knezevic, I.; Mattiuzzo, G.; Page, M.; Minor, P.; Griffiths, E.; Nuebling, M.; Moorthy, V. WHO International Standard for Evaluation of the Antibody Response to COVID-19 Vaccines: Call for Urgent Action by the Scientific Community. *Lancet Microbe* 2022, 3, E235–E240.
28. Taylor, P.C.; Adams, A.C.; Hufford, M.M.; de la Torre, I.; Winthrop, K.; Gottlieb, R.L. Neutralizing Monoclonal Antibodies for Treatment of COVID-19. *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* 2021, 21, 382–393.

29. Dhawan, M.; Priyanka; Parmar, M.; Angural, S.; Choudhary, O.P. Convalescent Plasma Therapy against the Emerging SARS-CoV-2 Variants: Delineation of the Potentialities and Risks. *Int. J. Surg.* 2022, 97, 106204.
30. Hodgson, S.H.; Mansatta, K.; Mallett, G.; Harris, V.; Emary, K.R.W.; Pollard, A.J. What Defines an Efficacious COVID-19 Vaccine? A Review of the Challenges Assessing the Clinical Efficacy of Vaccines against SARS-CoV-2. *Lancet Infect. Dis.* 2021, 21, e26–e35.
31. Bai, Z.; Cao, Y.; Liu, W.; Li, J. The SARS-CoV-2 Nucleocapsid Protein and Its Role in Viral Structure, Biological Functions, and a Potential Target for Drug or Vaccine Mitigation. *Viruses* 2021, 13, 1115.
32. Rak, A.; Donina, S.; Zabrodskaia, Y.; Rudenko, L.; Isakova-Sivak, I. Cross-Reactivity of SARS-CoV-2 Nucleocapsid-Binding Antibodies and Its Implication for COVID-19 Serology Tests. *Viruses* 2022, 14, 2041.
33. Westphal, T.; Mader, M.; Karsten, H.; Cords, L.; Knapp, M.; Schulte, S.; Hermanussen, L.; Peine, S.; Ditt, V.; Grifoni, A.; et al. Evidence for Broad Cross-Reactivity of the SARS-CoV-2 NSP12-Directed CD4+ T-Cell Response with Pre-Primed Responses Directed against Common Cold Coronaviruses. *Front. Immunol.* 2023, 14, 1182504.
34. Ayoub, A.; Thaurignac, G.; Morquin, D.; Tuailon, E.; Raulino, R.; Nkuba, A.; Lacroix, A.; Vidal, N.; Foulongne, V.; Le Moing, V.; et al. Multiplex Detection and Dynamics of IgG Antibodies to SARS-CoV2 and the Highly Pathogenic Human Coronaviruses SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV. *J. Clin. Virol.* 2020, 129, 104521.
35. Cook, N.; Xu, L.; Hegazy, S.; Wheeler, B.J.; Anderson, A.R.; Critelli, N.; Yost, M.; McElroy, A.K.; Shurin, M.R.; Wheeler, S.E. Multiplex Assessment of SARS-CoV-2 Antibodies Improves Assay Sensitivity and Correlation with Neutralizing Antibodies. *Clin. Biochem.* 2021, 97, 54–61.
36. den Hartog, G.; Schepp, R.M.; Kuijper, M.; GeurtsvanKessel, C.; van Beek, J.; Rots, N.; Koopmans, M.P.G.; van der Klis, F.R.M.; van Binnendijk, R.S. SARS-CoV-2-Specific Antibody Detection for Seroepidemiology: A Multiplex Analysis Approach Accounting for Accurate Seroprevalence. *J. Infect. Dis.* 2020, 222, 1452–1461.

